

Look before you leap: Comparison and profiles of hotel price determinants in four European markets

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Abstract

Pricing in the hospitality industry moves between adapting to a global demand and the need to manage locally. This double-edged challenge requires a managerial response based on flexibility and variety but one which is constrained by resources and competitive conditions. Since the sensitivity of each determinant may be different across types of hotels and countries, how hotel managers reach their compromises between determinants and countries remains an unsettled issue. Based on cross-nation methodology, we carry out a comparative analysis of price determinants from hotels in four main international tourist countries. The set of hypotheses developed are tested by estimating a quantile hedonic regression model with data from hotels in four countries. Results indicate that outcomes of pricing decisions differ by the country-of-operation, yielding a managerial profile per country. Also, the study estimates the contribution of the country to hotel pricing.

Keywords: Hotel pricing, Cross-nation, Differentiation, Agglomeration, Competition, Online reputation

1 **1.Introduction**

2 Hotel managers' pricing decisions can be understood as being rooted in a complex blend
3 of the hotel's own resources, the local environment, and certain destination specific
4 features. Thus, this study examines how hotels take advantage of differential pricing for
5 various international segments, as the market conditions differ among countries.

6 The hospitality industry is a key sector in Europe; four countries of Europe (i.e., Spain,
7 France, Italy, and UK) accounted for more than 73,000 hotels in 2021¹. Although the
8 hospitality and travel industry has been adversely affected by the COVID-19 crisis on a
9 global level, proactive strategic responses are needed to adapt business models to new
10 scenarios (Le & Phi, 2021). A comparative analysis of international hospitality
11 management reveals notable differences among countries regarding the problems and
12 challenges associated with the pandemic. Countries and cities did not experience the
13 pandemic's impact in the same way. For example, occupancy rates in America and Asia
14 fell further than in Europe (Statista, 2020a). Perceptions of COVID-19's effects on the
15 hospitality industry have revealed variations from one country to another due to cultural
16 differences (Shapoval et al., 2021).

17 From an international perspective, hotel price is also an essential factor for assessing
18 hospitality competitiveness among countries (e.g., World Economic Forum, 2019). The
19 literature has extensively discussed international pricing strategies from various
20 perspectives, such as the supply-demand framework (Mattila & Gao, 2016), competitive
21 environment (Becerra et al., 2013), profit maximization (Abrate et al., 2019), online

¹Specifically, the number of hotel establishments opened in Spain was 17,133 (INE, 2021), in France 17,165 (INSEE, 2021), in Italy 29,267 at the end of 2020 (Statista, 2020a) and 9,889 in UK also at the end of 2020 (Statista, 2020b).

22 channels (Moro et al., 2018), and channel intermediaries (i.e., travel agencies) (Stangl et
23 al., 2016).

24 Hotel pricing in an international context demands behavioural analysis of both consumers
25 and hoteliers. The heterogeneity of hotel clientele (Abrate et al., 2012), together with the
26 adoption of P2P platforms (Gibbs et al., 2018), foster a comparative approach to hotel
27 pricing in the international context. At the same time, hoteliers take advantage of
28 differential pricing because various markets have specific customer segments (Yelkur &
29 DaCosta, 2001). There are huge differentials in hotel pricing across different countries
30 (TheGlobalEconomy.com). Extant research about hotels location, though no
31 generalizable, evidence that frequently hotels in the same destination apply similar
32 pricing policies, rather than pursuing individualized pricing policies focused on the
33 specific hotel and tourists' characteristics (Vives & Jacob, 2021). Explanations are related
34 to hotels deal with similar revenue managers or prefer to cooperate with hotels already
35 established in the destination searching for common managerial practices (Woo & Mun,
36 2020).

37 Concerning extant literature on pricing determinants in an international context, and
38 despite extensive research on hotel pricing, there is a lack of studies that have addressed
39 the existence of country-level similarities and differences in the impact that determinants
40 have on price. Assaf et al. (2017) assess the determinants of hotel performance across
41 different destinations, Viglia & Abrate (2017) model price determinants in rural hotels
42 for several markets, Picazo & Moreno-Gil (2018) assess differences in package holidays
43 prices between Mediterranean countries, and Arora & Mathur (2020) analyse differences
44 across emerging and developed markets. The approach adopted in literature has rested on
45 hedonic pricing theory accounting for intra-hotel attributes, hotel type, reputation,
46 contextual factors, and country identification (n.b., see a review of this approach in Arora

47 & Mathur, 2020). Given hotels are ‘location bound’ (Whitla et al., 2007), with a
48 confirmed relevance of local factors for explaining hotel performance (Assaf et al., 2017),
49 we propose to enrich the existing approach in two ways: first, from a managerial
50 perspective, by including spatiality and competition factors, and second, from a
51 methodological approach, by adopting a cross-national analysis.

52 This study undertakes a cross-country analysis of pricing determinants, considering the
53 recommended guidelines for cross-national research (Cadogan, 2010), adopting a more
54 permanent and long-term perspective to avoid mispositioning of the hotel strategy (Melis
55 & Piga, 2017), and assuming the identification of countries as single markets (Arora &
56 Mathur, 2020). To approach the analysis empirically, we carried out comparisons of the
57 effects of price determinants in 2,650 hotels in four main European countries according
58 to their hospitality industry, using a quantile regression model to assess effects by
59 different pricing segments. Hence, we rather adopt a long-term pricing perspective (i.e.,
60 uniform pricing) instead of a short-term analysis focused on price tactics (i.e., dynamic
61 pricing), to adequately reflect the positioning of each hotel (Mitra, 2020), accounting for
62 the magnitude of tour operators’ demand (Vives & Jacob, 2020), and avoiding seasonality
63 bias.

64 This study aims to provide several contributions to the hospitality literature. First, our
65 study advances a new proposal to reduce the lack of moderators in the investigation of
66 hedonic price models (Arora & Mathur, 2020). Second, given the expansion of
67 international hotels and the need to mitigate the “liability of foreignness” (Woo & Mun,
68 2020), this study deals with several markets, overcoming the limitations of previous
69 studies based on a single market on issues such as quality signals-vs-reputation (Abrate
70 & Viglia, 2016), standardization-vs-differentiation (Yu et al., 2014), or agglomeration-
71 vs-competition (Lee & Jang, 2015). This study concludes by providing an economic value

72 of the country effect and outlining a per country generalization of pricing driver behaviors
73 (Cadogan, 2010).

74 **2.Literature background and research questions**

75 *2.1 Market price premium*

76 The tourism literature acknowledges the relevance of country image and reputation on
77 tourist behaviour. Country image directly affects tourists' visit intentions and indirectly
78 through tourists' beliefs about a country's products (Elliot & Papadopoulos, 2016) and
79 tourists' destination evaluations (Zhang et al., 2018). Additionally, different destinations
80 within a country may be linked to the country's master brand (Harish, 2010).

81 At the economic level, country economic performance positively influences hotel price
82 levels (Lee, 2011). Focusing on firm behavior, institutional theory (Scott, 2001) supports
83 the relevance of the institutional environment in organizational development.
84 Management research supports the influence of the national economy and country
85 environment on corporate governance practices (Daniel et al., 2012). Hotel literature has
86 indicated country institutional factors affect hotel management behavior and perceived
87 image, even more than the effects of local or industrial issues (Lee et al., 2017).

88 Hadad et al. (2012) conclude there are differences among developed countries associated
89 with labor productivity, while Assaf & Barros (2013) confirm the impact of hotel
90 ownership and location on hotel efficiency, concluding France, Spain, and the UK are
91 among the countries with the most efficient hotel industries. Papatheodorou (2002) found
92 resorts at Italian destinations are sold at a premium compared to Spanish destinations.
93 Poater & Garriga (2009) observed destinations located in Nordic countries are the most
94 expensive, followed by destinations located in Mediterranean countries, and the cheapest
95 destinations are in Central Europe. Hence, we advance the following hypothesis:

96 **H1:** The country-of-operation influences hotel price.

97 *2.2 Horizontal differentiation and country-of-operation*

98 Hospitality research has highlighted the tension between standardization-vs-
99 differentiation as a dilemma hoteliers must face given the industry's global context (Yu
100 et al., 2014). The expansion of international hotel chains (Woo & Mun, 2020) promotes
101 the standardization of services, especially in developed markets since they can thus attain
102 significant benefits (Yu et al., 2014) but tourists value the hospitality and service received
103 when there is a national identity element in the service provision (Ariffin et al., 2015).
104 Faced with this dilemma of standardization-vs-differentiation, strategic equilibrium
105 theory (Deephouse, 1999) posits hotels balance the differentiation strategy intensity based
106 on country conditions that legitimize the necessary adaptation level. In fact, some specific
107 services provided by hotels have a different impact on price depending on the country
108 (Arora & Mathur, 2020) and standardization can lead to strong price competition among
109 countries (Picazo & Moreno-Gil, 2018).
110 However, differentiation does not always have a positive impact on hotel performance
111 (Kim et al., 2020). Moreover, it has been confirmed that customers prefer international
112 chains over independent hotels (Gao et al., 2018). Given there is a high penetration of
113 international chains in developed European markets, except for Italy (Horwath HTL,
114 2018), we propose the following hypothesis:

115 **H2:** There is a moderating effect of the country-of-operation on the negative
116 relationship between differentiation and hotel price.

117 *2.3 Country differences in hotel system categories*

118 Extant hospitality literature has traditionally considered hotel category as the variable
119 with the greatest influence on hotel pricing, showing a positive impact on price and
120 considered as a proxy for the quality of the hotel as well as a protection factor against
121 price competition (Becerra et al., 2013).

122 However, hotel category has limitations when it comes to explaining hotel price (Abrate
 123 et al., 2011), its impact can be heterogeneous depending on the destination (Mathur,
 124 2019), and it is quite evident that there are differences from one destination to another for
 125 the same hotel category (Arora & Mathur, 2020). Additionally, there are multiple hotel
 126 classification systems worldwide with different criteria which generate heterogeneity
 127 within the same category (Minazzi, 2010; UNWTO, 2015). Table 1 highlights the
 128 differences between the classification systems in the four selected countries.

Criteria/Country	Spain	France	Italy	UK	References
Ruling organization	Regional governments	National government	Regional authorities	National government through Visit Britain/Visit England	UNWTO (2015) Minazzi (2010)
Criteria and implementation	261 criteria Mandatory System	246 criteria Voluntary system	55 criteria Mandatory system	498 criteria Voluntary system.	UNWTO (2015) Minazzi (2010)
Frequency of inspections	Only initial and when change of ownership	5 years	Depends on region	Annual	UNWTO (2015)

129
130

Table 1. Hotel classification system specificities for each country

131 Although hotel classification based on the number of stars is widely used to justify price,
 132 the diversity of classification systems among countries can cause heterogeneity in terms
 133 of its impact on price, limiting its validity as a proxy for vertical differentiation (Abrate
 134 et al., 2011). Moreover, inconsistencies have been found in the regulation of the hotel
 135 category in some markets (Núñez-Serrano et al., 2014), which may weaken its intensity
 136 as a quality signal. Therefore, the following hypothesis is raised:

137 **H3:** There is a moderating effect of country-of-operation on the positive
 138 relationship between star category and hotel price.

139 *2.4 Online reputation and country-of-operation*

140 Online reputation derived from user reviews has experienced a rapid rise as a quality
 141 signal in hotel booking (Yang et al., 2018). The factors identified to explain its increasing
 142 relevance are the limitations of category as a predictor of price and quality (Abrate et al.,

143 2011), the mismatch between expected quality level and category (Núñez-Serrano et al.,
144 2014), the predominance of physical standards based on establishment rather than service
145 levels (Minazzi, 2010) and the heterogeneous hotel classification systems indicated
146 previously (UNWTO, 2015). Indeed, hotel classification systems reveal a lack of
147 customer opinion integration (Blomberg-Nygaard & Anderson, 2016).

148 Online reputation complements hotel category by reducing possible information
149 asymmetries (Manes & Tchetchik, 2018). Travelers increasingly rely on reputation, using
150 online platforms to seek out the experiences and valuations of others and to share their
151 own (Yang et al., 2018). Consequently, online travel agencies (OTAs) have played a key
152 role in hotels achieving price premiums (Yacouel & Fleischer, 2012). Hoteliers take a
153 more tactical and less strategic approach by incorporating online reputation into their
154 price management (Abrate & Viglia, 2016). Indeed, previous literature confirms the
155 relevance of online reviews to hotel strategy and profitability, which are conditioned by
156 the hotel geographical context (Yang et al., 2018).

157 In other industries, the moderating role of national culture in the relationship between
158 online reputation and sales has been demonstrated. Particularly, Tang (2017) shows the
159 effect of online reputation is heterogeneous and is affected by the product country-of-
160 origin and by buyers' national cultural aspects, while Lin & Kalwani (2018) suggest
161 national culture moderates the occurrence of online reputation and its impact on product
162 sales. Additionally, the region of location exerts an influence on the online reputation of
163 the hotels (Banerjee & Chua, 2016) and country moderates the impact of some hotel
164 amenities on customer satisfaction (Moro et al., 2019). Finally, the penetration degree
165 and dependence on OTAs may present differences in European developed markets
166 (Stangl et al., 2016), which may moderate the incorporation of online reputation into price

167 management. To assess whether the national context affects the relevance and
168 consequences of the online reputation, the following hypothesis is proposed:

169 **H4:** There is a moderating effect of the country-of-operation on the positive
170 relationship between online reputation and hotel price

171 *2.5 Competition environment and country-of-operation*

172 Hospitality literature has identified the friction between two opposite effects on hotel
173 performance: agglomeration-vs-competition (Lee & Jang, 2015) with contradictory
174 findings. Agglomeration theories (McCann & Folta, 2008), which posit the benefits
175 associated with co-location of hotels next to one another, have been empirically supported
176 (Lee & Jang, 2015). However, the Industrial Organization theory (Shaked & Sutton,
177 1982), which posits the negative impact on hotel performance due to an increase in
178 competition, has also received support (Becerra et al., 2013; Lee, 2015).

179 From an international expansion perspective, this contradiction is a key factor in the
180 investment decisions of international hotels in foreign locations, as they prefer to choose
181 markets where they can achieve advantages (Assaf et al., 2015). Consequently, to
182 alleviate the “liability of foreignness”, international hotels seek locations where the
183 positive externalities due to agglomeration outweigh the negative externalities (Woo &
184 Mun, 2020). However, previous studies have not incorporated an international
185 perspective and are limited to a single market (Becerra et al., 2013; Falk & Hagsten, 2015;
186 Lee & Jang, 2015), even though the prevalence of positive externalities due to
187 agglomeration are dependent on aspects relating to markets, such as demand (Lee & Jang,
188 2015) and seasonality (Silva, 2016) that can moderate its effect.

189 Additionally, hotel agglomeration reveals different behavior patterns that require specific
190 analyses based on country (Marco-Lajara et al., 2014). The hotel location is affected by
191 the specific land use of countries (Fang et al., 2019) and hotel development is influenced

192 by urban planning (Luo & Lam, 2016). Since countries differ in their urban planning, we
193 can expect the country can moderate the positive effects of agglomeration, with the hotel
194 industry being the most dependent on locating in urban areas (Melo et al., 2009).
195 Additionally, there is cross-country evidence of the two-way relationship between
196 agglomeration and economic growth of the country (Krugman, 1991) and given our study
197 framework is in developed European markets; we postulate the following hypotheses:

198 **H5a:** There is a moderating effect of the country-of-operation on the positive
199 relationship between numbers of competitors and hotel price.

200 **H5b:** There is a moderating effect of the country-of-operation on the negative
201 relationship between distance between competitors and hotel price.

202 **3.Methodology**

203 *3.1 Variables and models*

204 Hotel information was collected using Veturis.com, an international Wholesaler that
205 groups several travel agencies focused on the transient travel market and hence Veturis
206 can be considered like other sources such as OTAs that have been widely considered due
207 to the availability of a wide range of hotel features (Latinopoulos, 2018). The final sample
208 included 2,650 hotels from Spain, France, Italy, and the UK.

209 The dependent variable **Price**, in accordance with previous studies (Hung et al., 2010;
210 Lee, 2015; Zhang et al., 2011) is the yearly average daily rate (ADR) for a standard double
211 room during the year 2017 because it measures the current price paid per room for each
212 lodging establishment and it is free of price variations caused by seasonal effects,
213 distribution channels and events (Lee, 2015). **Price** is log-transformed to consider a semi-
214 logarithmic model (Latinopoulos, 2018). For a continuous variable, the coefficient
215 multiplied by 100 provides the percentage impact on price while, for a dummy variable,
216 the percentage effect is computed by $100 \cdot (e^{\beta_i} - 1)$ (Halvorsen & Palmquist, 1980).

217 The following control variables, that have been widely considered in previous literature,
 218 are included in the hedonic price model: *Size=Number of hotel rooms* (Becerra et al.,
 219 2013); *Age=Hotel construction year* (Falk & Hagsten, 2015); *Hotel type* (aparthotel,
 220 hotel, and hostel), with aparthotel used as the reference (Falk & Hagsten, 2015); *N_Serv*
 221 *=Total number of services offered* (Latinopoulos, 2018) and *Urban_Hotel* (a dummy
 222 variable for urban hotels) (Falk & Hagsten, 2015).

223 The price determinants for regression analysis are:

- 224 • *Country dummy variables.* We included three dummy variables for France, Italy, and
 225 the UK (i.e., Spain is the reference) to control any unobservable difference between
 226 countries which may influence hotel price (hotel management, country economic
 227 performance, country international tourist arrivals).
- 228 • *H_Dif.* This variable measures the horizontal differentiation in the service space
 229 between hotels located in the same commercial zone from 0 (minimum differentiation)
 230 to 1 (maximum differentiation) with a measure based on the angular separation (Jaffe,
 231 1986) as follows:

$$232 \quad (H_Dif)_i = 1 - \max_{\substack{j \in A_i \\ j \neq i}} \left(\frac{V_i \cdot V_j}{\|V_i\| \cdot \|V_j\|} \right)$$

233 where A_i is the commercial area of hotel i and V_i is a vector with 71 dummy variables
 234 that represent the services offered by hotel i that includes hotel style, sport activities
 235 and food services.

- 236 • *Category.* This variable measures the official star rating of the hotel, from one to five
 237 stars and is the services quality indicator officially assigned by the corresponding
 238 agencies (Becerra et al., 2013).
- 239 • *Online_Reputation.* This variable, based on a reputational approach (Zhang et al.,
 240 2011) represents the yearly average online rating from customers of each hotel in 2017.

241 Each partner agency of Veturis group shows on its website the average rating given to
 242 each hotel. Veturis only allows real guests to post an online review after their hotel
 243 stay (Sánchez-Lozano et al., 2021) and hence it ensures a reliable and genuine measure
 244 of the online reputation.

245 • *Competition*. Each hotel's competition was computed by the number of lodging
 246 establishments within the same commercial area as the hotel divided by the logarithm
 247 of the number of overnight stays in the city where the hotel is located. (Sources:
 248 National Statistical Offices of all countries).

249 • *Distance*. For each hotel this variable provides the average distance, in kilometres,
 250 from hotels located in the same area divided by the surface in square kilometres of the
 251 city (Sources: National Statistical Offices of all countries) where the hotel is located
 252 (Becerra et al., 2013).

253 Table A.1 (Appendix A) contains the summary statistics for continuous variables and
 254 hotel distribution by country and hotel type.

255 We used moderated multiple regression (MMR), due to the advantages over alternative
 256 modelling (Schepers, 2016) to consider the following hedonic price models:

257 **Null_Model:**
$$\ln Price_i = \alpha_0 + \sum_{j=1}^6 \rho_j C_{ij} + \sum_{h=1}^3 \gamma_h D_{ih} + \sum_{j=1}^5 \omega_j X_{ij} + \varepsilon_i$$

258 **Alternative_Model:**
$$\ln Price_i = \alpha_0 + \sum_{j=1}^6 \rho_j C_{ij} + \sum_{h=1}^3 \gamma_h D_{ih} + \sum_{h=1}^4 \sum_{j=1}^5 \varphi_{hj} D_{ih} X_{ij} + \varepsilon_i$$

259 where C_j are the control variables, D_h the country dummy variables, X_j the independent
 260 variables and ε_i is the random error. *Alternative_Model* considers interactions with all
 261 countries.

262 The *Alternative_Model* requires homocedasticity across countries, confirmed by the
263 Breusch-Pagan test (Rosopa et al., 2016) (p -value 0.635). To prevent multicollinearity
264 with interactions terms, we standardized the exogenous variables subtracting the
265 respective mean. The variance inflation factors (VIF) did not detect multicollinearity
266 problems since all values were below 4.52 (Kennedy, 2008).

267 The estimation methods were OLS and quantile regression (Koenker, 2005). The latter
268 makes it possible to analyze which independent variables have a non-constant effect on
269 the conditional distribution of price and may be more efficient than OLS under non-
270 normality of residuals (Koenker, 2005). Shapiro-Wilk and Shapiro-France tests
271 confirmed the non-normality of the residuals for OLS. We conducted estimations with
272 the Barrodale-Roberts method (Koenker, 2005) at the 25th, 50th, 75th and 90th
273 percentiles due to the positive asymmetry of the hotel price sample distribution (skewness
274 value 9.70). Pseudo R^2 value (Koenker & Machado, 1999) was considered for goodness
275 of fit. For OLS and quantile regression, standard errors were estimated by bootstrap
276 methods (Davison & Hinkley, 1997; Feng et al., 2011). Figure 1 summarizes the statistical
277 analysis implemented with R version 4.1.2.

278

279

Figure. 1. Cross-country analysis methodology

280 **4.Results**

281 The first step was to analyze the overall moderating country effect through the
 282 significance of the *Alternative_Model* against the *Null_Model* (Figure 1). The F-test for
 283 OLS and the Wald test (Koenker, 2005) for quantile regression confirm an overall

284 moderating country effect (p -values below $2.2E-16$). Table A.2 (Appendix A) show the
 285 *Null_Model* (only 25th and 75th percentiles) and *Alternative_Model* estimation.

286 Regarding main country effect (**H1**), we performed a global test for significance of all
 287 coefficients corresponding to *Country dummy variables* with the *Alternative_Model* that
 288 confirmed in all models the main country effect (p -values below $2.2E-16$). Following
 289 Figure 1, we analyzed the differences between countries through cross-country pair
 290 comparison tests (results available from the correspondence author on request).

291 Results showed the UK has the highest country effect, being significantly different from
 292 all other countries. French effect is significantly higher than Spain and Italy, except at
 293 90th percentile where Italy and France do not show significant differences, whereas
 294 Italian effect is significantly stronger than Spain except at the 50th percentile, where both
 295 countries have the same effect. Due to the standardization of the exogenous variables, the
 296 main country effect is equivalent to the price premium in each country for hotels with
 297 mean values in the price determinants with respect to the Spanish price. Following
 298 Halvorsen & Palmquist (1980), Table 2 shows the percentage increase with respect to
 299 hotel price in Spain due to the main country effect.

Country	OLS	0.25	0.5	0.75	0.9
France	60.313	60.967	67.536	76.167	70.653
Italy	10.915	7.099	n.s.	15.610	41.046
UK	82.652	77.464	90.035	106.847	108.068

300 **Table 2.** Price premium in percentage for each country with respect to Spain

301 To test the hypotheses **H2-4** and **H5a-b**, we analyzed whether each exogenous variable
 302 has a significant effect (Figure 1) through an omnibus test for null interactions associated
 303 with each variable (Schepers, 2016). Table 3 shows results from the omnibus test for each
 304 independent variable and confirm a significant effect on price for all variables, except

305 H_Dif at the 90th percentile. Thus, differentiation has no impact on price for upscale
 306 hotels in all countries. The remainder of analysis excludes H_Dif at this percentile.

Variable	OLS	Quantile regression			
		0.25	0.5	0.75	0.90
H_Dif	H₀: $\omega_{H_Dif \times Spain} = \varphi_{H_Dif \times France} = \varphi_{H_Dif \times Italy} = \varphi_{H_Dif \times UK} = 0$				
<i>p</i> -value	0.061*	0.002***	0.028**	0.042**	0.905
Category	H₀: $\omega_{Cat \times Spain} = \varphi_{Cat \times France} = \varphi_{Cat \times Italy} = \varphi_{Cat \times UK} = 0$				
<i>p</i> -value	2.2E-16***	2.2E-16***	2.2E-16***	2.2E-16***	2.2E-16***
Online_Reputation	H₀: $\omega_{Online \times Spain} = \varphi_{Online \times France} = \varphi_{Online \times Italy} = \varphi_{Online \times UK} = 0$				
<i>p</i> -value	1.8E-10***	9.1E-7***	1.5E-13***	3.5E-5***	6.7E-6***
Competition	H₀: $\omega_{Comp \times Spain} = \varphi_{Comp \times France} = \varphi_{Comp \times Italy} = \varphi_{Comp \times UK} = 0$				
<i>p</i> -value	2.2E-16***	2.2E-7***	2.2E-16***	2.2E-16***	9.3E-11***
Distance	H₀: $\omega_{Agglo \times Spain} = \varphi_{Agglo \times France} = \varphi_{Agglo \times Italy} = \varphi_{Agglo \times UK} = 0$				
<i>p</i> -value	2.5E-7***	1.8E-4***	6.9E-5***	4.7E-5***	9.4E-4***

307 *p<0.1
 308 **p<0.05
 309 ***p<0.01

310 **Table 3.** Global significant effect in the *Alternative_Model*.

311 Next, we contrasted the moderating country effect for each explanatory variable with a
 312 significant joint effect through a global test for equality of interactions (Schepers, 2016).
 313 Table 4 shows results from the global test for moderating country effect.

314 Following Figure 1, for those variables with a significant effect and significant country
 315 moderation (Tables 3-4), Table A.2 (*Alternative_Model*) shows in which countries the
 316 variable effect is significant. For countries with significant variable effect, Table 5 shows
 317 the percentage impact on price per unit increase of the variable in each country. According
 318 to Tables 3-4, H_Dif at the 90th percentile was excluded from this analysis. For
 319 *Online_Reputation* at 25th percentile and *Distance* at 75th percentile, Table 5 only shows

320 the percentage change due to the variable effect without moderation from *Null_Model*.
 321 Similarly, Figure 2 shows the impact of each variable in each country. Finally, for
 322 variables with moderating country effect, we performed multiple comparisons between
 323 pairs for those countries where the specific variable has a significant effect (Figure 3).

Variable	OLS	Quantile Regression			
		0.25	0.5	0.75	0.9
H_Dif	H₀: $\omega_{H_Dif \times Spain} = \omega_{H_Dif \times France} = \omega_{H_Dif \times Italy} = \omega_{H_Dif \times UK}$				
p-value	0.092*	0.031**	0.069*	0.031**	No effect
Category	H₀: $\omega_{H_Dif \times Spain} = \omega_{H_Dif \times France} = \omega_{H_Dif \times Italy} = \omega_{H_Dif \times UK}$				
p-value	3.9E-10***	4.5E-4***	3.4E-4***	7.5E-5***	0.002***
Online_Reputation	H₀: $\omega_{H_Dif \times Spain} = \omega_{H_Dif \times France} = \omega_{H_Dif \times Italy} = \omega_{H_Dif \times UK}$				
p-value	2.5E-4***	0.154	8.4E-6***	0.020**	0.009***
Competition	H₀: $\omega_{H_Dif \times Spain} = \omega_{H_Dif \times France} = \omega_{H_Dif \times Italy} = \omega_{H_Dif \times UK}$				
p-value	2.2E-16***	2.7E-7***	2.2E-16***	2.2E-16***	1.2E-8***
Distance	H₀: $\omega_{H_Dif \times Spain} = \omega_{H_Dif \times France} = \omega_{H_Dif \times Italy} = \omega_{H_Dif \times UK}$				
p-value	0.009***	0.019**	0.007***	0.120	0.067*

324 *p<0.1
 325 **p<0.05
 326 ***p<0.01

327 **Table 4.** Omnibus test for moderating country effect.

328 Concerning *H_Dif*, Table 4 shows moderation by country in its impact in all models
 329 except at the 90th percentile (upscale hotels), so **H₂** is broadly confirmed. For OLS and
 330 lower midscale hotels (50th percentile) *H_Dif* has a null effect in all countries except in
 331 Spain where *H_Dif* has a significantly negative effect (Table 5, Figure 2). For economy
 332 hotels (25th percentile), *H_Dif* only has a significant negative effect in Spain and the UK
 333 where economy hotels can achieve a price premium through the standardization.

Variable	Spain	France	Italy	UK
OLS				
H_Dif	-20.225*	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
Category	16.181***	23.053***	39.773***	33.058***
Online_Reputation	7.475***	n.s.	n.s.	6.620***
Competition	1.536***	n.s.	-0.215*	-2.323***
Distance	n.s.	-108.102***	-213.181***	-50.508***
P25				
H_Dif	-16.701***	n.s.	n.s.	-65.930***
Category	13.818***	20.850***	23.068***	34.493***
Online Reputation (No moderation)			5.951***	
Competition	1.314***	-1.776**	n.s.	n.s.
Distance	n.s.	-260.444***	-129.483**	-20.430*
P50				
H_Dif	-18.745***	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
Category	17.005***	26.312***	32.702***	31.405***
Online Reputation	6.864***	n.s.	n.s.	9.240***
Competition	1.991***	-2.185**	n.s.	-2.928***
Distance	-25.576*	-223.663***	-167.203*	-42.889***
P75				
H_Dif	n.s.	n.s.	42.393***	n.s.
Category	19.635***	24.912***	46.806***	30.306***
Online Reputation	7.505***	n.s.	n.s.	9.582**
Competition	1.987***	n.s.	n.s.	-4.249***
Distance (No moderation)			-46.811	
P90				
H_Dif (Null effect)			n.s.	
Category	22.523***	25.583***	45.480***	30.706***
Online Reputation	7.645***	n.s.	n.s.	9.408**
Competition	1.780***	n.s.	-0.550**	-4.151***
Distance	-42.100***	n.s.	-344.452***	-66.534***

334 *p<0.1

335 **p<0.05

336 ***p<0.01

337 **Table 5.** Percentage impact on price per unit increase for variable and country.

338 In most cases, the effect of *H_Dif* is null or negative. Only for Italian upper midscale
339 hotels (75th percentile), the effect is significantly positive whereas in the other countries,
340 its impact is not significant. Consequently, services standardization is not
341 counterproductive for hotel pricing and differentiation only allows prices to be increased
342 in Italian upper midscale hotels.

343

344

Figure 2. Variable effect by model and country.

345

Category has a significant overall difference in the impact on price due to the country for

346

all models, which confirms **H3** (Table 4). Since *Category* effect is always positive (Table

347

5, Figure 2), the moderation only influences its intensity. The stronger effect occurs in

348

Italy and the UK without significant differences (Figure 3), except at 75th and 90th

349

percentiles where Italy has the stronger effect. The lowest effect occurs in Spain, except

350

at the 75th and 90th percentiles where Spain and France have the same effect. Thus, the

351

hotel category is confirmed as a quality signal but without global validity (Arora &

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Mathur, 2020) since even in developed markets its effect can show considerable

353

differences.

354

355

Figure 3: Effect difference significance between pairs of countries

356

Regarding *Online_Reputation*, its effect is moderated by country except for economy

357

hotels (Table 4), where the positive effect is the same for all countries (Table 5, Figure 2)

358

so **H4** is broadly confirmed. Since its effect is positive or null, the moderation only

359

influences the effect intensity. *Online_Reputation* shows the same significantly positive

360

effect in Spain and the UK in all models (Figure 3). The French and Italian effects are

361

null except for the economy hotels mentioned above. Therefore, there are differences in

362

the extent of influence of online reputation on price in the countries analyzed.

363

Regarding *Competition*, there is a significant moderating country effect in all models

364

(Table 4), so **H5a** is confirmed. The Spanish effect is positive (Table 5, Figure 2) with

365

significant differences with the rest of countries (Figure 3) where the effect is null or

366

negative. In the UK, the effect is significantly negative for all models except at 25th

367 percentile. The Italian effect is negative only for OLS and 90th percentile. In France, only
368 at 25th and 50th percentiles the effect is negative. In all other cases, the effect is null.
369 Thus, the country moderation influences both the intensity and the valence of the effect.
370 Among countries with significantly negative effect, only for OLS and 90th percentile
371 there are significant differences between Italy and the UK.

372 Concerning *Distance*, its effect is moderated by country in all models except at 75th
373 percentile (Table 4) which broadly confirms **H5b** (Table 4). In all countries, *Distance* has
374 the same negative effect for upper midscale hotels (i.e., the shorter the distance to
375 competitors, the higher the price) (Table 5, Figure 2) whereas in all other cases the effect
376 is negative or null in all countries, so the moderation only influences the effect intensity.
377 For OLS, only the difference between the UK and Italy is significant (Figure 3). For
378 economy hotels, the UK has a significantly lower effect intensity than France and Italy.
379 For 50th percentile, only the differences between Spain and France and between UK and
380 France are significant. Finally, for upscale hotels the strongest effect occurs in Italy,
381 followed by the UK and Spain with significant differences for all pairs comparisons.

382 To analyze the existence of a global agglomeration effect (i.e, positive impact on price
383 due to an increase in *Competition* and a decrease in *Distance*) Figures 5-9 display the
384 percentage impact on price due to a percentage increase in *Competition* mean and
385 percentage decrease in *Distance* mean.

OLS

386

387 **Figure 4.** OLS percentage impact on price per percentage increase in *Competition* mean
388 and percentage decrease in *Distance* mean.

P25

389

390 **Figure 5.** P25 percentage impact on hotel price per percentage increase in *Competition*
391 and percentage decrease in *Distance* mean.

392

393 **Figure 6** P50 percentage impact on price per percentage increase in *Competition* mean
 394 and percentage decrease in *Distance* mean.

395

396 **Figure 7** P75 percentage impact on price per percentage increase in *Competition* mean
 397 and percentage decrease in *Distance* mean.

398

399 **Figure 8** P90 percentage impact on price per percentage increase in *Competition* mean
 400 and percentage decrease in *Distance* mean.

401 Figures 4-9 show that there is a global agglomeration effect (red area) in Spain and Italy
 402 in all cases, in France for OLS and 25th percentile, and in the UK only for economy
 403 hotels. On the other hand, the blue area suggests a global competition effect (i.e negative
 404 effect due to an increase in *Competition* and a decrease in *Distance*) in French economy
 405 hotels and in the UK in all cases except for economy hotels, since there is only a positive
 406 impact on price if the distance can decrease considerably for small increases in
 407 competition (red area). Finally, the global agglomeration effect is null for French upscale
 408 hotels.

409 Spain has the strongest global agglomeration effect in all cases, followed by Italy except
 410 for the 75th percentile where the Italian and French effects do not show a significant
 411 difference. On the other hand, the global competition effect shows greater intensity in the

412 UK except for economy hotels where in the UK there is an agglomeration effect and in
413 France a competition effect.

414 Given the heterogeneous impact of some determinants due to the country, the overall
415 market price premium with respect to Spain (i.e., the percentage increase in price due to
416 the market for hotels with the same characteristics) may be heterogeneous. When there is
417 a significant country moderation for a specific determinant X_j , following Halvorsen &
418 Palmquist (1980), we computed the market price premium with respect to Spanish hotels
419 as a function of X_j (i.e., other explanatory variables ceteris paribus) as follows:

$$420 \quad \text{Country Price Premium (\%)} = \frac{Price_{Country} - Price_{Spain}}{Price_{Spain}} \times 100$$
$$421 \quad = (\exp(\gamma_{Country} + (\varphi_{Country j} - \varphi_{Spain j}) \cdot X_j) - 1) \times 100$$

422 where $\gamma_{Country}$ denoted the main country effect and $\varphi_{Country j}$ denotes the coefficient for X_j
423 in the specific country. Otherwise, the market price premium is the main country effect.
424 Spain is the reference because it is the country with the lowest main country effect in all
425 models.

426 Figure 9 displays for all models the country price premium as a function of each
427 determinant. Given that differentiation is not moderated by the country for upscale hotels,
428 the price premium remains at the values provided by Table 2 whereas for 75th percentile
429 is similar in the case of France and the UK but not for Italy whose price premium can
430 improve considerably through high differentiation. For OLS and 50th percentile the price
431 premium for all countries respect to Spain are negatively influenced by standardization,
432 which is similar for economy hotels, except in the UK, where the standardization allows
433 to achieve higher price premiums compared to the rest of countries.

434 Concerning Category, Figure 9 shows the UK price premium is the highest in most cases
435 and the heterogeneity of the Italian price premium that it is negative with respect to Spain

436 for 1- and 2-star hotels and it is positive from 3 to 5-star hotels (except at 50th percentile
437 where price premium is positive from 4-stars hotels). Even for upscale hotels, it is higher
438 than the French price premium for 5-star hotels.

439 French and Italian price premium decreases as the level of online reputation increases
440 (Figure 9) and Italian price premium can even be negative. Thus, French, and Italian high
441 reputation hotels command smaller market price premium than low reputation ones,
442 which usually attain the highest price premium, except for economy hotels which
443 command static price premium due to lack of moderation. The price premium for UK
444 midscale and upscale hotels is positively influenced by online reputation while for OLS
445 it is negatively influenced.

446 Regarding *Competition*, all countries suffer a decrease in the price premium respect to
447 Spain, which can become negative for high values of *Competition*. The sharp falls in
448 French economy and lower midscale hotels and British hotels (except for economy hotels)
449 stand out.

450 Concerning *Distance*, price premium respect to Spain is stable for 75th percentile in all
451 countries due to lack of moderation. For all other models, premiums in all countries can
452 improve respect to Spain by locating in crowded areas, except for French upscale hotels
453 whose price premium experiences a strong increase as *Distance* increases.

454

455

Figure 9. Country price premium (%) as a function of each determinant.

456

5. Conclusions and limitations

457

Prior research has shown the relevance of both international competitiveness and the image of hotels (Lee et al., 2017) as well as their local knowledge and adaptation to countries of operation (Woo & Mun, 2020). Also, the overall relevance of online information for travelers (Yang et al., 2018) and due to the utmost relevance of location and spatial concentration decisions (Marco-Lajara et al., 2014), we base on cross-nation methodology to elucidate the differential effects of strategic hotel pricing decisions depending on the country-of-operation. Thus, we performed a comparative analysis with

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463

464 a wide dataset of hotels in four countries. Our findings are based on a quantile regression
465 analysis that contemplates heterogeneous effects over price distribution. We provide a
466 new perspective to hotel pricing research by showing how country can moderate some
467 relationship(s) between determinants and price even in developed markets.

468 *5.1 Theoretical implications*

469 Firstly, our work encompasses several markets, which has allowed us to analyze in a
470 broader context the role played by each price determinant in a more universal way finding
471 out which determinants have a more globalized role, and which are more local in hotel
472 pricing management in developed markets, thus surpassing limitations from previous
473 studies. Second, our study contributes to reducing the lack of moderator identification in
474 previous hotel price hedonic studies (Arora & Mathur, 2020) and highlights the
475 moderating role of the country in the effect intensity of some determinants and even its
476 valence, which allows us to delve deeper into the country-level differences. Additionally,
477 our results expand on the previous studies (Arora & Mathur, 2020) that confirm the
478 existence of a price premium associated with the country, providing us with a novel
479 finding that this premium is not homogeneous for all hotels in the same country and its
480 magnitude can depend on reputational attributes, location in relation to competitors, and
481 the services on offer.

482 Regarding the standardization-vs-differentiation confrontation (Yu et al., 2014), given
483 that the effect of differentiation in most cases is negative or null, it is confirmed that the
484 service standardization in developed markets is a determinant that allows either to
485 increase prices (economy hotels in UK and Spanish lower midscale hotels) or to provide
486 benefits by saving the cost of implementing additional services or offering them for free
487 (Lin, 2017). Only in the Italian upper midscale hotels does the differentiation of services

488 allow prices to be increased, which may be supported by the lower penetration of
489 international chains in this market (Horwath HTL, 2018).

490 As expected, the global role of hotel category as a quality signal to reduce information
491 asymmetry (Manes & Tchetchik, 2018) is confirmed. Although, the intensity of its effect
492 is moderated by country, which can be partly explained by its different regulation, even
493 in developed markets (Table 1). In Spain, it has lost significant validity, which may be
494 due to the inconsistency in the regulations (Núñez-Serrano et al., 2014).

495 The heterogeneity in the degree of online reputation incorporation in price management
496 is verified, except for economy hotels. The UK is the market with the strongest inclusion
497 of online reputation as price determinant followed by Spain, which partly compensates
498 the loss of validity of Spanish category as a quality signal (Manes & Tchetchik, 2018),
499 being a less strategic and more tactical market whereas in the UK, the incorporation of
500 online reputation in price management has not reduced the validity of the category. France
501 and Italy are purely strategic markets (except for economy hotels) that only consider
502 category as a reputational signal (Abrate & Viglia, 2016).

503 Finally, regarding agglomeration-vs-competition confrontation (Becerra et al., 2013;
504 McCann & Folta, 2008), results show that in developed markets, the benefits from
505 locating close to competitors outweigh the negative effects of competition, except in
506 French economy and lower midscale markets and in the UK markets (except in economy
507 hotels). Thus, both intensity and valence of the global agglomeration effect is moderated
508 by the country. Given the null or negative role of differentiation in services, our results
509 extend previous studies about which agglomerations are more beneficial (Lee & Jang,
510 2015), since they confirm that undifferentiated hotel agglomerations can obtain more
511 benefits than differentiated ones in developed markets, except for the case of Italian upper
512 midscale hotels for which differentiated agglomerations are more beneficial.

513 *5.2 Managerial implications*

514 First, hotel managers and international chains that operate in developed markets must bet
515 on undifferentiated service offers with respect to competitors, except for those that
516 operate in the Italian upper midscale market. Additionally, they must locate near to
517 competitors due to the benefits that they can obtain relating to price (with the exceptions
518 noted above). Second, given the relevant role that the agglomeration effect has on the
519 investment decisions of international chains, the Spanish and Italian hotel markets are the
520 most attractive regarding the decision about investing in new properties in developed
521 markets. On the contrary, France (for economy and lower midscale hotels) and the UK
522 are the least attractive markets due to the global competition effect. Finally, hotel
523 managers operating in the UK and Spain must implement a more dynamic and tactical
524 price management, incorporating online reputation compared to the more static nature of
525 the French and Italian market and Italian (except for economy hotels) (Abrate & Viglia,
526 2016). These insights allow us to propose a differentiated pricing dashboard for each
527 country and price cluster (Figure 2).

528
529 *5.3 Limitations and future research*

530 This study includes some limitations that can direct future research. First, the countries
531 included have a tourism sector with a high level of competitiveness (World Economic
532 Forum, 2019). Future research should consider other less competitive developed markets
533 to strengthen the results obtained from our work through a global understanding of the
534 moderating role of country in the impact of price determinants.
535 Second, the study provides evidence of the moderation role of country on price
536 determinants through a simplistic incorporation of dummy variables. Future research
537 could explore alternative ways of examining the specific national factors that influence
538 price determinants. Third, our study shows the heterogeneity effect of online reputation

539 on price according to country, but future research should incorporate the origin of
540 customers' online reviews since its effect is influenced by cultural and national customer
541 aspects (Tang, 2017). Finally, our study has considered annual prices assuming a static
542 approach for hotel price, future research should consider the incorporation of the dynamic
543 nature of hotel price.

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756

757 **Appendix A: Sample descriptive statistics and model estimation**

Variable	Mean	St. dev.	Median	Min	Max
lnPrice	4.370	0.494	4.288	3.305	7.204
Size	109.5	117.900	79	3	1989
Age	2000	25.065	2004	1575	2017
N_Serv	3.332	3.219	3	1	28
H_Dif	0.978	0.114	1	0	1
Category	3.405	0.796	4	1	5
Online_Reputation	7.383	1.114	7.500	0.200	10
Competition	5.408	10.396	1.824	0.060	62.903
Distance	0.028	0.079	0.010	0	2.617
Hotel_type\Country %	Spain	France	Italy	UK	
Urban_Hotel	56.203	61.475	65.196	73.333	
Hotel_type\Country %	Spain	France	Italy	UK	
Aparthotel	8.074	1.639	0.490	1.905	
Hotel	91.230	97.814	99.510	97.619	
Hostel	0.695	0.546	-	0.476	

758

759

Table A.1. Sample descriptive statistics.

	OLS	0.25		0.5	0.75		0.9
	Alternative	Null	Alternative	Alternative	Null	Alternative	Alternative
Intercept	5.016***	4.347***	4.713***	4.760***	5.661***	6.278***	7.953***
France	0.472***	0.470***	0.476***	0.516***	0.616***	0.566***	0.534***
Italy	0.104***	0.007	0.069**	0.027	-0.048	0.145**	0.344***
UK	0.602***	0.582***	0.574***	0.642***	0.864***	0.727***	0.733***
Size	1.4E-4**	2.4E-4***	2.6E-4***	1.0E-4	1.5E-4	2.0E-5	1.5E-4
Age	-3.3E-4	-1.7E-4	-3.6E-4	-2.5E-4	-5.2E-4	-8.1E-4	-0.001**
Hotel	-0.181***	-0.093***	-0.056	-0.116***	-0.280***	-0.299***	-0.622***
Hostel	-0.313***	-0.169**	-0.127	-0.214*	-0.233	-0.378***	-0.670***
N_Serv	0.002	-0.004*	-0.001	0.001	0.001	0.004	0.009*
Urban_Hotel	-0.017	0.020	0.010	-7.0E-4	-0.002	-0.030	-0.064**
H_Dif		-0.103***			-0.059		
Category		0.169***			0.231***		
Online_Reputation		0.060***			0.054***		
Competition		0.003***			0.009***		
Distance		-0.472**			-0.468***		
H_Dif×Spain	-0.202*		-0.167***	-0.187***		-0.078	-0.013
H_Dif×France	-0.030		0.111	0.213		0.216	-0.106
H_Dif×Italy	0.285		0.089	0.165		0.424***	0.366**
H_Dif×UK	-0.232		-0.659***	-0.112		0.114	0.090
Category×Spain	0.162***		0.138***	0.170***		0.196***	0.225***
Category×France	0.231***		0.209***	0.263***		0.249***	0.256***
Category×Italy	0.398***		0.231***	0.327***		0.468***	0.455***
Category×UK	0.331***		0.345***	0.314***		0.303***	0.307***
Online_Reputation×Spain	0.075***		0.087***	0.069***		0.075***	0.076***
Online_Reputation×France	0.017		0.033	-1.0E-4		0.009	0.002
Online_Reputation×Italy	-0.004		0.032	0.030		0.008	-0.050
Online_Reputation×UK	0.066***		0.052**	0.092***		0.096**	0.094**
Competition×Spain	0.015***		0.013***	0.020***		0.020***	0.018***
Competition×France	-0.010		-0.018**	-0.022**		-0.005	-0.003
Competition×Italy	-0.002*		-0.001	-9.0E-5		-0.001	-0.006**
Competition×UK	-0.023***		-5.0E-4	-0.029***		-0.043***	-0.042***
Distance×Spain	-0.239		-0.161	-0.256*		-0.199	-0.421***
Distance×France	-1.081***		-2.604***	-2.237***		-0.417	-0.123
Distance×Italy	-2.132***		-1.295**	-1.672*		-1.851**	-3.445***
Distance×UK	-0.505***		-0.204*	-0.429***		-0.554***	-0.665***
R²	0.3967	0.2319	0.2571	0.2713	0.2392	0.2858	0.3107